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Приказ / Review
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Review: Nemanja Mitrović, *Challenging Decade: Yugoslav-Romanian Relations 1948–1958* (in Serbian: *Decenija iskušenja: Jugoslovensko-rumunski odnosi 1948–1958*), (Belgrade: Institute of Contemporary History, 2024), pp. 607

Romania is one of the few Balkan countries Serbia/Yugoslavia did not wage war with, even during the terrible years of World War II. After the war, both Yugoslavia and Romania became socialist countries, and it seemed nothing would endanger close relationships. However, Belgrade and Bucharest had rather turbulent relations during the first decade and a half after 1945. These turbulences are the subject of the new book by Nemanja Mitrović, *Challenging Decade: Yugoslav-Romanian Relations 1948–1958* (in Serbian: *Decenija iskušenja: Jugoslovensko-rumunski odnosi 1948–1958*), published by the Institute of Contemporary History in Belgrade in 2024. Nemanja Mitrović earned his PhD in History at the Faculty of Philosophy in 2023. He is an emerging scholar in contemporary Serbian historiography, carving out a significant niche in the study of Yugoslav-Romanian relations during the Cold War. His BA, MA, PhD theses, as well as the previous monograph, all dealt with the same topic.¹

¹ Graduation thesis: Yugoslav-Romanian relations: Meetings and conversations between Josip Broz Tito and Nicolae Ceausescu in 1968; Master's thesis Yugoslav-Romanian relations: Meetings and conversations between Josip Broz Tito and Nicolae Ceausescu during 1969 and 1970; Doctoral thesis: Yugoslav-Romanian relations 1954– 1968; Book: Tito – Ceausescu: Years of Rapprochement: Yugoslav-Romanian relations 1968–1970.

Mr. Mitrović follows bilateral relations between two neighbors in a uniquely challenging decade for both countries. However, to properly understand Yugoslavia and Romania, one must realize their position in 1945. As the author explains in the first aptly-named chapter, *Under Stalin's overcoat* (Serbian: *Ispod Staljinovog šinjela*, pp. 19–61), Yugoslavia and Romania became a part of a wider network of USSR-controlled countries in Eastern and Southeastern Europe. Both countries adopted Soviet-style communism and blind obedience to Stalin.

However, the starting year for Mr. Mitrović's original research, 1948, is one of the most consequential years in communist history. It was the year of the famous Tito-Stalin split, the first crack in the communist block. In a short amount of time, Yugoslavia was ostracized from other communist countries. Communist Romania was the most extreme in its anti-Tito actions: the author vividly describes how the Yugoslav-Romanian border resembled a warzone with barbed wire, trenches, and frequent armed incidents. Furthermore, the Romanian press published thousands of articles denigrating Tito and the Communist Party of Yugoslavia, while the Serbian minority in Romanian Banat was subjected to harassment, show trials and even deportation to the deserted area of Baragan. The author states that Romanian anti-Yugoslav hysteria was fueled by their fear of Stalin.

Stalin's death in 1953 effectively ended the split. New Moscow leadership started mending the rift with Belgrade. However, Romania was very cautious to renew the relations with its western neighbour, fearing the new Soviet stance towards Tito was a passing phase. They were finally convinced in 1955, with the Belgrade and Moscow Declarations as well as the Twentieth Congress of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union, and the following de-Stalinization process that occurred in the USSR. Finally, Romania and Yugoslavia were ready to renew their "mythical friendship". However, the stimulus had to come from the highest echelons of both communist parties. That happened in 1956 when Yugoslav leader Tito visited Bucharest, and his Romanian counterpart Gheorghe Gheorghiu-Dej reciprocated by visiting Belgrade. Two delegations signed several key treaties in Bucharest and the Adriatic island of Brioni, restarting economic cooperation. However, the 1956 Hungarian Revolution endangered the warming of relations. Belgrade and Moscow clashed about

the fate of Hungarian leader Imre Nagy, and Romania was expected to follow Moscow's leadership. However, by the late 1950s, Romania was ready to step away from Moscow's shadow and open itself to the West. Yugoslavia's contacts and experience would prove invaluable. Therefore, Bucharest leadership did not want to completely break contact with their Belgrade counterparts. The book's closing year, 1958, saw Soviet troops leaving Romania, which allowed the country to lead more autonomous foreign policy and commit itself to severely improving relations with Yugoslavia in the next decade.

The author has adopted a chronological-thematic approach to this topic, which makes it easier for readers to follow the presentation and understand the cause-and-effect relationships between events. Additionally, readers can easily find specific aspects of Yugoslav-Romanian relations that interest them, such as sports, cultural or economic exchanges, or visits by high-ranking officials from both countries. While it might be expected for a book of this nature to take a dry, fact-based approach, the author skillfully avoids this. As illustrated in the chapter "Under Stalin's Overcoat," he demonstrates a refined sense of language and stylistic elements, making the book more accessible to general readers. A significant value of this book lies in the extensive efforts Dr. Mitrović invested in archival research. He has explored materials from all the major archives in Serbia. Although the COVID-19 pandemic hindered his ability to access unpublished archival material in Romania, he largely compensated by consulting published archival materials from Romania. To grasp the spirit of the times, Dr. Mitrović also examined contemporary journalism from both countries, focusing on primary newspapers like *Borba* and *Scantea*. His in-depth understanding of Yugoslav-Romanian relations and the effort he put into illuminating this topic is evidenced by the inclusion of over six hundred bibliographical references at the end of the book.

This book is primarily intended for individuals seeking a deeper understanding of the crucial decade in relations between Belgrade and Bucharest. However, it is also suitable for scholars at universities or research institutes, as well as students of 20th-century history and interested laypeople. The author has made an effort not only to provide the historical context of the relations between the two countries but also to

integrate them into the broader historical framework. The book emphasizes that to fully comprehend the dynamics of Yugoslav-Romanian relations during this period, one must also consider the influence of a third party: the Soviet Union. Thus, these relations can be visualized as occurring within a triangle, with Moscow as a pivotal point. Finally, the author includes summaries in Serbian, English, and Romanian, making his findings accessible to the international scholarly community.

In conclusion, Dr. Mitrović's comprehensive research, along with his engaging narrative style, makes this book an essential resource for those looking to understand the complex dynamics of Yugoslav-Romanian relations during a crucial period in Cold War history.